

A REVIEW ARTICLE ON AZARDIRACHATA INDICA LINN.

(ENGLISH NAME MARGOSA TREE)

Dr. Deependra Sharma, * Dr. Meena Varma and **Dr. Prasanna Purohit

Asst. Prof. at GMERS Medical Collage, Valsad, Gujrat, *Department of Biochemistry, MGM Medical College and Associate Hospital, Indore and **Dr. A. P. J. Abdul Kalam University Indore M.P.

English name Margosa Tree (Local name: Neem) found all over India the Tree measures around 8 to 10 mts. Oil is extracted from the seed leaves fall in winter and in autumn new reddish tender leaf appears. External skin astringent but internal is pungent. The bark contains a bitter resin called Margosin. It also contains a volatile oil, gum, white secretion, sugar and an astringent element. Seed contains 40% stable oil and traces of Sulphur. Leaves and bark is antimicrobial. It removes foul smell, reduces burning sensation and itching. Seed oil has wound healing, antileprotic, analgesic, therefore it is used in treatment of abscess, lymphadenitis, ulcer. In pruritis hot water bath with decoction of neem leaves is given. Neem oil is also used as massage oil. The fruit is purgative. Leaves are anti-helminthics and stimulant of liver functions. Its Bark decoction with honey is useful in jaundice, anorexia vomiting, dysentery, intestinal worms, liver diseases. Ointment preparation from seed is applied in piles. The Fruit is useful in constipation. Leaves are more useful in excessive mucous secretion. Bark decoction is used in chronic cough. 30 to 60 cc of liquid collected from the trunk is given in T.B. and leprosy. It is also useful in Diabetes. Its seed is uterine stimulant. Seed powder is used in dysmenorrhea and puerperium. The juice of neem leaves should be given to postpartum women just after delivery as it is a uterine tonic. It is useful in all skin condition especially in burning and irritation sensations.

Brihat Samhita, an ancient Hindu treatise, contains a chapter on plant medicines. It contains recommendations for specific trees to be planted in the vicinity of one's house. Neem was highly recommended. It can be easily cultivable in every part of India. Each and every part of this tree has some medicinal property so used in different disease states. Neem, a major herbal ingredient in Ayurvedic preparations, has been used in India for over 4000 years. Neem has historically been used to help the body fight both temporary and chronic conditions.

Neem trees have many unique compounds that have been identified and others that are as yet unidentified, most analyzed compounds are-

Nimbin (C₂₈H₄₀O₈) - Anti-inflammatory, anti-pyretic, anti-histaminic, anti-fungal.

Nimbidin – Anti – tuberculous, anti-protozoal, anti-pyretic.

Gedernin- Vasodilator, anti-malarial, anti-fungal.

Sodium Nimbinate – Diuretic, spermicidal, anti-arthritis

Queceretin – anti-protozoal.

Salannin – repellent

Azadirachtin – repellent, anti-feedant, anti-hormonal.

The uses of neem are remarkably diverse. In India, the sap is used for treating fevers, general debilitation, digestive disturbances, and skin diseases; the bark gum for respiratory diseases and other infections; the leaves for digestive problems, intestinal parasites; the fruit for debilitation, malaria, skin diseases, and intestinal parasites; and the seed and kernel oil for diabetes, fevers, fungal infections, bacterial infections, inflammatory diseases, fertility prevention, and as an insecticide. (Stix G. Village pharmacy.1992) (Neem Foundation)

NEEM leaf is a traditional herb used for treating diabetes and has been scientifically proven to be effective in treating and preventing diabetes. Oral doses of NEEM leaf extracts significantly reduced insulin requirements for non-insulin dependent diabetes. NEEM oil has also proven effective and has been able to inhibit increases in blood sugar levels by as much as 45% in test animals. Capsules containing NEEM and a number of other herbs are currently available in many countries for the treatment of diabetes. In tests to verify the effectiveness of the medication, it was found that blood sugar was lowered by over 50% in twenty weeks and maintained thereafter. NEEM leaf extracts have been shown to reduce insulin requirements of diabetics without apparent effect on blood glucose levels. Different studies show insulin requirement reductions of between 20 percent and 50 percent for those who take NEEM leaf capsules. There are even anecdotal reports of diabetics chewing a single dried NEEM leaf daily that have been able to eliminate insulin injections completely. Based on the many studies of NEEM's effects on insulin requirements, the Indian government has approved the sale by pharmaceutical companies of NEEM tablets for diabetics.

(Siddqui, 1945) & Santhoskumari, 1990, observed that Neem leaf tea significantly reduces the need for insulin.

Skula, R. et al., (1973) published his work on preliminary clinical trials on antidiabetic action of Neem oil. This showed the effect of neem leaf capsules on diabetics as follows-

1. Two severe juvenile diabetics- no effect
2. Five Insulin dependent diabetics- 30-50% reduction of insulin requirement

Neem leaf extract is a traditional herb for treating diabetes (**Alam, et al., 1989**) and has been scientifically proven effective in treating & preventing diabetes; (**Murty, 1978**); (**Chakrabarty, 1984a**). Oral doses of leaf extracts significantly reduced insulin requirements for non-insulin depended diabetes. (**Pillai, 1981 b**); (**Luscombe, 1974**); (**Murty (1978)**).

Aqueous extract of neem leaves significantly decreases blood sugar level and prevents adrenaline as well as glucose-induced hyperglycemia. (**Murthy, K.S. et al 1978**)

A significant hypoglycemic effect was also observed by feeding neem oil to fasting rabbits. (**Pillai, N. R. et al 1981b**)

Oral administration of nimbidin demonstrated significant hypoglycemic effect in fasting rabbits. (**Pillai, N. R and Santhakumari, G., 1981**). Administration of Neem oil at 200 mg/rat produces severe hypoglycemic effect. (**Jacobson, M., 1995**).

Neem oil has also proven effective and has been able to inhibit increase in blood sugar levels (**Sharma, 1983**). He observed that the Neem oil:

- Lowered FBS 26% in normal rats made hyperglycemic
- Inhibited the rise in blood sugar 45% in normal hyperglycemic rabbits given a glucose meal
- Had a 33.7% inhibiting effect on raising blood sugar in rats made hyperglycemic by adrenaline injection
- Prevented rise in blood sugar by 28% in diabetic rats

Bhargava, A.K. (1987) in his research work demonstrated that Neem oil worked as a synergist to antidiabetic drug for the management of secondary hyperglycemia.

Aqueous leaf extract also reduces hyperglycemia in streptozotocin diabetes and the effect is possibly due to presence of a flavonoid- quercetin. (**Chakraborty et al 1989**)

The aqueous leaf extract when only fed, also produces hypoglycemia in normal rats and decreased blood glucose levels in experimentally –induced diabetes in rats.

In “**The Yoga of Herbs**” (1992, Lotus Press) by David Frawley and Vasant Lad states that Neem oil can be used in skin diseases (urticaria, eczema, ring worm), Parasites, malaria fever, cough, thirst, nausea, vomiting diabetes, tumours, obesity, arthritis, rheumatism and jaundice. They also observed that Neem is one of the most powerful blood– purifiers and detoxifiers in Ayurvedic usage.

Neem and a number of other herbs currently available lowered the blood sugar by over 50% in twenty weeks and maintained thereafter (**Saraf, 1993**).

Banerjee, 1992 & Jaiswal et al., 1994 explained the effect as anti-anxiety for Neem oil because of its action on increase serotonin in brain & observed that anxiety induced type – 2 D.M. may be reduced.

Oral administration of neem oil at 200mg/rat produces severe hypoglycemic effect. (**Jacobson, M et al 1995**)

Effect of epinephrine on the increment index calculated from intravenous glucose tolerance tests and on hepatic glycogen before and after neem leaf extract treatment was studied in normal and streptozotocin-induced diabetic rabbits. Neem leaf extract, in itself, was found to have no action on peripheral utilization of glucose or on hepatic glycogen. The reduction in peripheral utilization of glucose and glycogenolytic effect due to epinephrine action was blocked by *A. indica* leaf extract, however, almost completely in diabetic rabbits and to a certain extent in normal ones. (**Chattopadhyay, R. R., J. Ethnopharmacol. 1996, 27, 431-434.**) Effect of *Azadirachta indica* leaf extract on serotonin inhibition in glucose mediated insulin release in rat pancreas was studied in vitro to elucidate the possible mechanism of antihyperglycemic effect of *A. indica* leaf extract. *A. indica* leaf extract blocks significantly ($P < 0.05$) the inhibitory effect of serotonin on insulin secretion mediated by glucose. (**Chattopadhyay, R. R., J. Ethnopharmacol., 1999, 67, 373-376.**)

Recently, hypoglycemic effect was observed with leaf extract and seed oil, in normal as well as alloxan-induced diabetic rabbits. (**Khosla, P et al 2000**)

Hypoglycemic effect was observed with *Azadirachta indica* when given as a leaf extract and seed oil, in normal as well as diabetic rabbits. The effect, however, was more pronounced in diabetic animals in which administration for 4 weeks after alloxan induced diabetes, significantly reduced blood glucose levels. Hypoglycemic effect was comparable to that of glibenclamide. Pretreatment with *A. indica* leaf extract or seed oil administration, started 2 weeks prior to alloxan, partially prevented the rise in blood glucose levels as compared to control diabetic animals. The data suggests that *A. indica* could be of benefit in diabetes mellitus in controlling the blood sugar or may also be helpful in preventing or delaying the onset of the disease. (**Khosla P, Bhanwra S, Singh J, et al, 2000.**)

Preliminary clinical trials on antidiabetic actions of *A. indica* by **Dr. Rajesh Shukla, Dr. Surinder Singh and Dr. C.R. Bhandari** also showed the hypoglycemic effect of neem.

Hypoglycemic effect of neem seed oil on the blood glucose concentration in alloxan diabetic rats was described.

Lowering of blood sugar by water extract of *A. indica* and *Abroma augusta* in diabetic rats is described by **Halim EM. (Jun 2003)**

Gupta et al (Feb 2004) described the protective role of extract of neem seeds in diabetes caused by streptozotocin in rats.

Lat et al 1936 observed that one of the actions of Neem oil is antifertility.

Chopra et al, 1952 reported its antibacterial action. Its spermicidal action is reported by **Sinha, et al., 1984. Bhargava et al., 1985** demonstrated its wound healing property and its mechanism of wound healing, it increases the capillary permeability at the site of wound healing & enhances wound healing.

“Medicinal Plants of India & Pakistan” (1988, **D.B. Taraporevala Sons and Co.**) by **J.F. Dasture** defines the Neem as carminative, expectorant antihelminthic, antidotal, diuretic, discutient and insecticidal in skin disease & Jaundice. It is mentioned that it acts in chronic malarial fever because of its action on liver. It can be used as a stimulant, antiseptic and antispasmodic. It is also given in phthisis, leprosy and general debility. It is also recommended for urinary disease & piles.

In “The way of Herbs” [1990, **Pocket Books**], by **Michael Tierra** it is observed that terpenoids such as azadirachtins, triterpenoid bitters, tannins & flavonoids acts as anti-inflammatory antipyretic, antihelminthic & astringent, antibacterial and antiviral agent.

In Planetary Herbology (1942, Lotus Press), Michael Tierra defines anti-inflammatory as “Counteracting or diminishing inflammation or its effects”, antipyretic, “dispels heat, fire and fire”, antihelminthic, “helps destroy and dispel parasites (includes vermicides and vermifuges)” and astringent “firms tissues and organs, reduces discharges and secretions.”

Toxins produced by bacterial infection are relieved by Neem’s anti-bacterial compounds (Patel and Trivedi, 1962).

Neem oil acts as blood purifier and has widest range of beneficial effects (Vohora, 1986). It is believed to remove toxins from the blood & promote a healthy circulation (Chattopadhyay, et al., 1992 a) Small amounts of Neem oil have been found to protect the liver from damage. When toxic agents were used to induce hepatocellular necrosis (Chattopadhyaya, et al., 1992 b). Neem also can oxidize the blood to promote healing (Etkin, 1981).

Puri, 1993, observed that Neem oil can prevent kidney problems like infections or damage by high blood pressure, when taken with plenty of water. This helps the body fight infections and lowers blood pressure, allowing the kidneys to perform under less stress.

Several studies indicate that possible toxicity resulting by Neem oil is very low, especially when taken orally (Bhargava 1970); (Okpanyi, 1981).

Tests on animals required by the Environmental protection agency showed that alcohol extracts of the seed produced no external irritation in rabbits and no toxic effects on mice when taken internally, even in very large amounts (Larson, 1987).

Studies indicates that Neem oil when ingested, experienced nausea & general discomfort by some individuals (Chopra, 1965) perhaps due to Sulphur compound found in oil. Excessive consumption of raw Neem oil has been implicated in reduced liver function. (Thompson, 1978); (Okpanyi, 1981).

The toxic effects of Neem oil consumption has been disputed (Larson, 1987) by some researchers that believe contamination with aflatoxin or inadvertent additions of the oil of the chinaberry tree, a related species to Neem which is known to be toxic, is the cause of the observed side effects (Quadri, 1984); (Jongen, 1983). Neem oil taken orally or vaginally after intercourse has been found to possess anti-implantation and abortifacient effects. So pregnant women or those who are trying to conceive should never ingest Neem oil & should also avoid using it intra – vaginally. Neem is generally considered an extremely safe product, because it has been used for centuries in India. It is used in tooth paste & as tooth brush and placed with food to protect against insects. No danger has been documented. Children in India and Africa eat Neem fruit with great enjoyment during its fruiting season. Rats treated with Neem oil in laboratory studies actually gained weight instead of showing ill effects.

A German study showed that using of Neem oil from clean Neem seeds showed no toxicity at doses of 50,000 mg per kg (Neem, 1992) or more. Tests undertaken for the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency before the approval of a commercial Neem product, Margosan – o, showed no or limited toxicity to rats, ducks, rabbits & bees. Studies have revealed that it may cause toxic encephalopathy particularly in infants and young children. The usual features are vomiting, drowsiness, tachypnoea & recurrent generalized seizures. Leukocytosis & metabolic acidosis. It may cause Reye’s syndrome and toxic liver injury because of increased mitochondrial permeability. Reye’s syndrome is characterized by hyperammonemia, hypoglycemia micro-vascular steatosis & encephalopathy. Neem tree is profusely available in the dry forest of Deccan plateau; besides this it is also available in the rest of India. The growth of Neem is comparatively less in Punjab. For providing clean air & shadow this tree is grown near houses & villages and by the side of roads. The leaves are 22.5 cm to 37.5 cm in length. It is smooth and it is imparipinnate, leaflets are 9-15. The leaves are deeply serrated.

Relative Sp gravity at 25°C is -0.900-0.920, Refractive Index at 25°C is – 1.44 to 1.48, Acid value – 22, Iodine value – 65-70, Saponification value – 196-200.

In the bark of Neem tree, chemicals known as Margosine, Nimbidin, Nimbin, Nimbinin and Nimbosterol are present. It also has 6 % Tannin. The tannin is also present in its flower. In the Neem oil (Margo oil) has oleic acid 49-61%, linoleic acid = 2-15%, Palmitic acid – 12-15%, Stearic acid = 14-21% and Nimbosterol 0.03%.

During the course of the freedom movement in India, led by Mahatma Gandhi, there was an upsurge of the 'Swadeshi' or nationalistic sentiment and with this pioneering research work on Neem was conducted. This led to a move to encourage 'Swadeshi' science. Neem research in India was a part of this movement. Pioneering work on the possible commercial use of neem and neem cake was done by the Indian Institute of science in Bangalore during the 1920s. Until 1933, neem cake was used in the sugar cane fields as a fertilizer and to keep termites at bay. At this point synthetic pesticides and remedies appeared in the market and overshadowed the pioneering work of indigenous science. Mahatma Gandhi however kept the tradition of Neem alive. He was known to be a firm believer in the goodness of Neem. Dr Ekaid, in reply to some queries about neem leaves by Gandhi, wrote. "We have made experiments upon neem leaves in our laboratory which revealed that its leaves contain more nutritious elements than any other similar vegetation which had been subjected to chemical analysis earlier". The prayer meetings at the Sabarmati Ashram were conducted under a Neem tree by the Mahatma Gandhi and Neem leaf chutney was a part of his everyday diet.

REFERENCE:

1. Stix G Village pharmacy. The neem tree yields products from pesticides to soap. *Sci Am.* 1992; 266:132.
2. Michael Tierra – Planetary Herbology (1942, Lotus Press). Neem Foundation.
3. Siddiqui, S. (1945) –*Journal of Scientific and Industrial Research.* 4:5-10.
4. Santhoshumari, K.S., Devei, K.S.– *Ancient science of life,* (1990) 9(4): 221-22.
5. Skula, R-Singh, S & Bhandari, CR. – *Medicine & Surgery* (1973) 13:11-12.
6. Murty, K.S. Rao, D.N., Rao, D.K. and Murthy, L.B.G. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology.* 1978 10: 247-250.
7. Chakarborty (1984a) *Prod. Nat. Symp. On Applied Biotech of Med. Aromatic Timber Yeilding Plants.* 12-13 Jan, 1984 PP. 370-380.
8. Pillai, N.R. and Santhakumari, G. *Indian Journal of Medical Research* 1981 74:931-933.
9. Luscombe, (1974) *Journal of Pharmacy & Pharmacology.* 26: suppl. 111.
10. Jacobson, M., in the *Neem Tree: Source of unique natural products for integrated pest management, Medicine, Industry and other purposes* (ed. Schmutterer, H.), 1995, pp.484-495.
11. Sharma, M.K., Khare, A.K. and Feroz, H (1983) *Nagarjun* 26:247-250.
12. Bhargava, A.K.– *Neem Newsletter,* 4(3): 31-32. s (1987)
13. Chakraborty T. Uerotta, L. and Poddar, G. *Phytotherapy, Res.,* 1989, 3, 30-32.
14. David Frawley and Vasant Lad: *The Yoga of Herbs* (1992, Lotus Press).
15. Saraf, et al – *Study of effect of “Karnim” in patients of NIDDM,* (1993)

16. Banerjee, S, (1992) – Naturwissenschaften, Feb; 79(2): 81-4.
17. Jaiswal, et al., Indian Journal of Experimental Biology –1994 32: 489-491.
18. Chattopadhyay, R.R., Gen. Pharmacol., 1996, 27, 431-434.
19. Khosla P, Bhanwra, S, Singh J Seth, S. And Srivastava, R.K. Indian J. Physiol. Pharmacol. 2000; 44:69-74.
20. Halim EM Indian Journal Exp Biol 2003 Jun; 41 (6):636-40.
21. Gupta S., Kataria M., Gupta PK, Murganandan S, Yashroy RC Ethnopharmacology 2004 Feb ; 90(2-3):185-9.
22. Lat et al. 1936 – India Journal of Pharmacology.
23. Chopra et al., A, – Indian Journal of Medical Research (1952) 40: 511-515.
24. Sinha. Indian Journal of Medical Research 1984 79:131-136
25. J.F. Dastur Medicinal Plants of India and Pakistan (1988, D.B. Taraporeval a, Sons & Co.).
26. Michael Tierra – The way of Herbs (1990, Pocket Books).
27. Michael Tierra – Planetary Herbology (1942, Lotus Press). Neem Foundation.
28. Patel, R.P. and Trivedi, – Indian Journal of Medical Research (1962) 50:218-222.
29. Vohora, S.B.– Hamdard. Vol. XXVIII, No. 1, 72-84. (1986).
30. Etkin, N.A. – Journal of Ethnopharmacology, 1981 4:75-98.
31. Puri, H.S. (1993). Therapeutic uses of Neem.
32. Bhargava, K.P., Gupta, M.B. – Indian Journal of Medicinal Research (1970) 58: 724-730
33. Okpanyi, S.N. and Ezenkwa, G.C. (1981) – Plant Med. 41:3-39.
34. Larson, R. O. – 3rd International Neem conference, July 10, 1986 PP.240-250
35. Thompson. Journal of Pharmacological Science (1978) 67: 1476-1478.
36. Quadri, et al (1984) – Int. Pest Control 26:18-20.
37. Jongen, et al – Environnemental Mutagenèses, 1983 5 : 687-694.